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Family educational backgrounds and family support in basic VET: students' perception

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Abstract

Through this communication we intend to relate the educational background of the families of basic VET students with the support that these students perceive their families offer them for their professional education and training. Having this main objective, we will expose data that allow us to outline the state of the issue on the basis of the empirical evidence obtained in the field work developed in the research "Success and dropout pathways in vocational training educational systems levels 1 and 2" (EDU2013-42854-R). Overall, the results presented allow us, firstly, to describe the families of basic VET students in terms of the educational level attained. Secondly, the crossing of this variable with the various aspects through which we describe students' perception about the family support allows us to evidence differences related to the educational background of the families.

Keywords

vocational education; educational background; family support; student's perception

1 Family educational background and student's perception of family support

Following Castel's work (1997), both labor integration and the strength of the relationships among individuals and their family and social environments determine the situation of integration, vulnerability or exclusion. Basic VET, as one of the measures addressed to attend diversity, prioritizes the permanence in the educational system, even if it implies the reduction of demands and expectations. Permanence by itself, despite reducing school failure rate, does not allow students to gain neither personally nor professionally achievements due to the constraints to develop a career. Thus, this educational context generates a type of devalued citizenship, which keeps basic VET students in a space of social vulnerability.

This paper is focused on the influence of family context on the decisions and itineraries of basic VET students. The approach to the family accounts for the relationship between their educational background and the student's perception of family support.

In relation to the family educational background, data about our educational system show the relevance of the educational level of the mother. Specifically, in 2017 the rate of Early School Leaving was located in the 3.8% in the case of young people whose mothers reached higher education, moving to a 11.3% in the case of post-compulsory secondary education, 20.7% for those whose highest level attained was compulsory secondary education, and 37.3% when they had maximum primary studies (Ministerio de Educación, Cultura y

Deporte, 2018). The data obtained through the questionnaires may enable us to transfer these analyses to basic VET in the Valencian region.

1.2 The research: main framework and methods

The data that we present in this paper have been obtained in the framework of the research project “Success and dropout pathways in vocational training educational systems levels 1 and 2” (EDU2013-42854-R). The objectives of this project, in which are involved the Universitat de les Illes Balears, the Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona and the Universitat de València, are aimed at describing those students that attend VET and the conditions that involve the development of their itineraries in this training, as well as to develop proposals to reduce school failure and early school leaving.

In order to fulfill these objectives, our research team is developing a longitudinal study in which we monitor students who began their studies in the academic year 2016-17 in VET systems 1 and 2 in a specific territory (in our case, in the Valencian region). As specific research methods, we are handing out questionnaires to the students and interviewing teachers and the management team of the educational organizations. We have completed this approach with data analysis in order to contextualize the phenomenon studied.

The data on which we base the analysis presented in this paper correspond to the results of the first pass of questionnaires, which was conducted between November 2016 and February 2017. In the definition of the research sample, we conducted a stratified sampling by conglomerates based on three criteria: the professional branch of the program, the location of the educational organization and its ownership. On the whole, this allows us to have a representative sample of VET level 1 and 2 in the Valencian region. Specifically, in VET level 1 we have 737 students distributed in 71 classes of 41 educational organizations and in VET level 2 we have 1240 students distributed in 85 classes of 43 organizations. In most of these organizations, both VET level 1 and 2 are taught. We will present here the data concerning VET level 1 (basic VET).

The theoretical framework of the research is based on the concept of student’s engagement. In order to approach the concept, we consider four dimensions: affective, behavioral, cognitive and academic (Appleton, Christenson, Kim & Reschly, 2006). These dimensions are on the basis of the Questionnaire 1 (Q1). The questions relating to student engagement were complemented with questions relating to socio-demographic characteristics (age, sex, family situation). On the whole, this allows us to relate the context, the student engagement and, when data of Q2 and Q3 are available, also with the itineraries performed by the students.

2 Main results

As explained above, the results presented are based on the results obtained in the Q1. We start with the description of the basic characteristics of the sample concerning the educational background of the mother and father (figure 1).

Figure 1 Student’s distribution by educational level of their parents

Data show that the educational level of the families stands around the Secondary Education: 50.9% of mothers and 49.2% of fathers are in the first three levels. It is also significant to highlight the students’ lack of knowledge of their parents’ educational level: 15.9% in the case of mothers, 21.7% in the case of fathers.

In order to broaden this description, we have crossed variables to see the answers of the students regarding their perception of the family support based on their educational level. Specifically, we present in the figures below the results for two items: "My family is available when I need it" (figure 2 and 3) and "When I have problems in high school, my family is willing to help me" (figure 4 and 5).

Figure 2 Agreement / disagreement with “My family is available when I need it” by level of studies of the respondent's mother

Figure 3 Agreement / disagreement with “My family is available when I need it” by level of studies of the respondent's father

Figure 4 Agreement / disagreement with “When I have a problem in High School, my family is willing to help me” by level of studies of the respondent's mother

Figure 5 Agreement / disagreement with “When I have a problem in High School, my family is willing to help me” by level of studies of the respondent's father

The data show that the students' perception is positive, prevailing in all the educational levels of their parents the agreement with the statements raised. We could point out slight differences in the several educational levels in those answers that indicate disagreement; although the general trends remain quite similar. In this sense, therefore, the educational level of the families does not seem to be determinant in the students' perception of the support. In fact, this trend is maintained in other similar statements of the questionnaire such as: "When something good happens at High School, my family wants to know", "My parents (or persons who fulfill their functions) expect to continue my studies for as long as possible"; "For my parents (or persons who fulfill their functions) it is important that I pass the course".

However, it should be also noted that there is a statement in which this trend varies: "My parents (or persons who fulfill their functions) know when I have homework or tests" (figures 6 and 7). Here, there is a higher rate of disagreements. Although we have only a descriptive approach, we could think about differentiating the perception of family support with the follow-up that may involve actions such as knowing when the student has homework or exams. In view of these data, students perceive support from their families although they are not involved in the school issues per se. Therefore, this support could be related to the training program more than with the day-to-day student's reality.

Figure 6 Agreement / disagreement with "My parents (or persons who fulfill their functions) know when I have homework or tests" by level of studies of the respondent's mother

Figure 7 Agreement / disagreement with “My parents (or persons who fulfill their functions) know / disagree when I have homework or tests)” by level of studies of the respondent's father

In order to deepen the results and transcend the descriptive scope, the research team is currently working on the data analysis. In this regard, an inferential analysis is being carried out in order to be able to interpret the results. For now, we can point out that in terms of significance the first analyses indicate that students with mothers without studies are the group with the lower perception of family support and parental commitment. In the same vein, students with fathers without studies show a perception of less parental commitment than other students. However, for this group, the differences in family support are not statistically significant. All in all, these results suggest that we need to complete these statistical analyses with a qualitative approach to deepen in the results.

3 Brief conclusions

The description of the data presented here allows us to conclude in two ways: first, we may affirm that basic VET families have mainly an educational level that could be placed at level 0-2 of ISCED11. Secondly, regarding the students' perception of family support, a positive perception stands out, and it is quite similar in all the educational levels.

However, we need more approaches and analysis to deepen this study. For instance, regarding the inferential analysis that are being carried out, we may wonder if the educational context still do not include in their curricular design those actions needed in order to integrate those families with lower educational levels in the school context. Therefore, the continuity of this research goes through questionnaires 2 and 3 and through a qualitative approach through group interviews and discussion groups that will allow us to delve into the results with the purpose of obtaining interpretative keys about the students' engagement and also to be able to assess the role that family plays in the students' itineraries.

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